

A Simple Physical Proof of the Triviality of a Large Class of Scalar Field Models in Euclidean Lattice Quantum Field Theory

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Abstract

We present a mathematical proof, based on a few physically reasonable hypotheses and the central limit theorem of mathematical statistics, that a large class of scalar field models in lattice quantum field theory are trivial in the continuum limit, in three or more spacetime dimensions, in the sense that all their expectation values can be obtained from related purely Gaussian models. This then implies that in the continuum limit there are no inter-particle interactions in these models, and therefore that under quantization they all reduce to theories of free particles, a situation known as the triviality of the models. It should be noted that the triviality argument presented here is completely independent of the representation of lattice quantum field theories by ensembles of random walks, which seems to be the representation used in most triviality-related arguments.

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1 Introduction

The problem of the triviality of the polynomial scalar field theories is a longstanding one. The basic numerical facts associated to this have been known for a long time [1,2]. Until recently there was still no complete analytical proof of triviality in the particularly important case of the quartic model in four-dimensional spacetime, but a rather involved proof for five or more dimensions was published more than four decades ago, in 1981 [3,4]. The quartic model in four-dimensional spacetime is particularly important since this model appears as part of the standard model of particle physics, and drives the process of spontaneous symmetry breaking that is a central feature of that standard model. The quartic model was addressed in a more recent paper, using the same techniques of the 1981 papers [5].

We present here a simple mathematical argument, based on a few physically reasonable hypotheses and the very famous and important central limit theorem (CLT) of mathematical statistics, that leads to the conclusion that a large class of scalar field models in Euclidean lattice quantum field theory are trivial, in the sense that all their expectations values are identical to those that can be obtained from corresponding Gaussian models, with quadratic Lagrangian densities. This then implies that there are no inter-particle interactions in these models, and that when quantized they reduce to just theories of free particles. The argument is based on three physical hypotheses that are quite simple and fairly non-controversial. These three hypotheses are, in general terms, as follows.

Hypothesis 1: consider the two-point function $g_2(\vec{n}_2 - \vec{n}_1)$ of the dimensionless field $\varphi(\vec{n})$, on finite N -lattices, where \vec{n} are the dimensionless integer lattice coordinates of the lattice sites, as this function is calculated in quantum field theory,

$$g_2(\vec{n}_2 - \vec{n}_1) = \left\langle \varphi(\vec{n}_1)\varphi(\vec{n}_2) \right\rangle - \left\langle \varphi(\vec{n}_1) \right\rangle \left\langle \varphi(\vec{n}_2) \right\rangle. \quad (1)$$

We assume that this function has a finite and non-zero value at the origin $\vec{n}_2 - \vec{n}_1 = \vec{0}$, that is, we assume that the number

$$g_2(\vec{0}) = \left\langle \varphi^2(\vec{n}) \right\rangle - \left\langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \right\rangle^2, \quad (2)$$

is a finite and non-zero positive number, the same at all sites \vec{n} , both for every finite value of N and in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ continuum limit. Note that $g_2(\vec{0})$ is the squared width of the distribution of the random variable $\varphi(\vec{n})$, so that this hypothesis also implies that the width (or covariance) of that distribution is finite.

Hypothesis 2: consider the two-point function $G_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1)$ of the dimensionfull field $\phi(\vec{x})$ which, as we will see later on, is related to the dimensionless field by the scaling relation $\phi(\vec{x}) = \varphi(\vec{x})/a^{(d-2)/2}$, still on finite N -lattices, where $\vec{x} = a\vec{n}$ are the dimensionfull real lattice coordinates of the lattice sites and a is the lattice spacing, as this function is calculated in quantum field theory,

$$G_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1) = \left\langle \phi(\vec{x}_1)\phi(\vec{x}_2) \right\rangle - \left\langle \phi(\vec{x}_1) \right\rangle \left\langle \phi(\vec{x}_2) \right\rangle. \quad (3)$$

We assume that in the $N \rightarrow \infty$, $a \rightarrow 0$ continuum limit the function $G_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1)$ is a Green's function, and hence is singular at the origin $\vec{x}_2 = \vec{x}_1$ and is finite and non-zero everywhere else, that is, for $\vec{x}_2 \neq \vec{x}_1$.

Hypothesis 3: we assume that the definition of the quantum field theory is that given on the Euclidean lattice, which we will describe momentarily, and that the physical

interpretation of the theory is that given by the process known as block renormalization, which takes us from the fundamental field $\varphi(\vec{n})$ to the average field $\bar{\varphi}(\vec{n})$ over blocks of sites of a given fixed size, thus determining a fixed length scale, and leading to an effective action $S_E[\bar{\varphi}]$ at such a length scale, for all its possible values.

These hypotheses will be further developed, refined and better described in what follows. We will use in our argument the very well-known and very important central limit theorem (CLT) of mathematical statistics, which we describe here in plain language, in a simple form that is appropriate for the use that we will make of it.

Central Limit Theorem: given an infinitely large set of random variables which are statistically independent from each other, and which are also identically distributed (known as **iid** random variables), with a distribution that has a finite width (or finite variance), the average of a number n of these variables is also a random variable, one which has a statistical distribution that, in the $n \rightarrow \infty$ limit, approaches very fast a simple Gaussian distribution (also known as a normal distribution). This distribution contains only two relevant parameters, an average value and a width that decreases with n as $1/\sqrt{n}$, regardless of the form of the statistical distribution of the original set of random variables.

Stating it with a little more precision, consider an infinite set of **iid** random variables X_i , whose distribution has average given by $\langle X \rangle = \bar{X}$ and squared width given by $\langle (X - \bar{X})^2 \rangle = \sigma^2$, both of which are assumed to be finite. Consider now an average \bar{X}_n over a subset of n such random variables, given by

$$\bar{X}_n = \frac{1}{n} \sum_i^n X_i, \quad (4)$$

which we might refer to as partial averages of size n . The variable \bar{X}_n is also a random variable, with a certain distribution of values. Consider now the shifted and rescaled random variable given in terms of \bar{X}_n by

$$\bar{Y}_n = \sqrt{n} (\bar{X}_n - \bar{X}). \quad (5)$$

What the theorem states is that in the limit in which $n \rightarrow \infty$ the distribution $\mathcal{D}[\bar{Y}_n]$ of values of \bar{Y}_n converges to the normal distribution $\mathcal{N}[\bar{Y}]$, that is, to a Gaussian distribution with zero average, so that we have that the partial average \bar{X}_n converges to the average \bar{X} , and with a finite and non-zero squared width given by σ^2 .

The reason for the definition of the rescaled variable \bar{Y}_n is to make its width constant along the limit, since the width of \bar{X}_n goes to zero in the limit. In this way the Gaussian nature of the limiting distribution becomes more immediately apparent. Since it is Gaussian, the distribution of these rescaled variables in the limit is given, up to a normalization constant, by $\exp(-\alpha \bar{Y}^2)$ with some finite and non-zero coefficient $\alpha > 0$. If we imagine for a moment that this could be a non-Gaussian distribution, given for example by an expression such as $\exp(-\alpha \bar{Y}^2 - \lambda \bar{Y}^4)$, including a quartic term with a coefficient $\lambda \geq 0$ in the exponent, then the statement of the theorem is that the constant λ goes to zero in the $n \rightarrow \infty$ limit.

This theorem can be found in any modern textbook on probability and mathematical statistics, such as [6], but usually expressed in a more technical mathematical language.

2 Definition of the Theory

Here we will give the definition of the theory. If we are to make any meaningful and precise statements about any theory, it is imperative that we start from a precise mathematical definition of that theory. We will use as the definition of the quantum field theory its realization on a discrete Euclidean lattice. In this constructive definition a discrete version of the theory is set up on finite lattices in a d -dimensional Euclidean space, in a way which is valid for arbitrarily large values of the linear integer size N of the lattice. The corresponding theory in the Minkowski continuum is obtained when we make the lattice infinitely large and its mesh infinitely fine, and execute a Wick rotation from the resulting Euclidean space to the corresponding Minkowski spacetime.

In order to define the theory and establish the notation, we will consider a discrete Cartesian lattice with N sites in each one of d spacetime directions, hence with a total of N^d sites and dN^d links between neighboring sites. Roughly speaking, the lattice is a discrete representation of spacetime. For simplicity we will give the definition for the case of a single-component scalar field, but the definition can be readily extended to fields with several components. If the components of the d -vector \vec{n} are the d discrete integer coordinates of the lattice sites in d dimensions, then the lattice field $\varphi = \varphi(\vec{n})$ is defined as a real function of these discrete coordinates, where

$$\vec{n} = (n_1, \dots, n_d), \quad (6)$$

$$n_\mu = 1, \dots, N, \quad (7)$$

$$\mu = 1, \dots, d, \quad (8)$$

and where $\varphi(\vec{n})$ is a single-component real scalar field, which in the lattice formalism is always a dimensionless quantity. The relevant geometrical elements of the lattice itself are its sites \vec{n} and the links l_μ between neighboring sites along the Cartesian direction μ . We assume that periodic boundary conditions are used on the lattice, meaning that along any given direction μ the site $n_\mu = N + 1$ is identified with the site $n_\mu = 1$, and that the site $n_\mu = 0$ is identified with the site $n_\mu = N$. Given a site \vec{n} and a direction μ , the link l_μ simply connects the site \vec{n} to its neighboring site $\vec{n} + 1_\mu$ in that positive direction, and is the natural locus for the finite difference of the two values of the field at either site. Here 1_μ represents the coordinate change at the link from the site \vec{n} to its next neighbor in the positive direction μ , going from a given value of n_μ to the value $n_\mu + 1$.

Given a dimensionless scalar field $\varphi(\vec{n})$, the Euclidean action functional defining the scalar field theory on the lattice is given, in the d -dimensional discrete position space defined by the lattice, by the expression

$$S_N[\varphi] = \sum_{\vec{n}}^{N^d} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mu=1}^d [\Delta_\mu \varphi(\vec{n})]^2 + \frac{\alpha}{2} \varphi^2(\vec{n}) + \vartheta[\varphi(\vec{n})] \right\}, \quad (9)$$

where the sum over \vec{n} runs over all N^d lattice sites, so that it can be expressed as a d -dimensional multiple sum,

$$\sum_{\vec{n}}^{N^d} \equiv \sum_{n_1=1}^N \dots \sum_{n_d=1}^N, \quad (10)$$

and where the dimensionless potential $\vartheta[\varphi(\vec{n})]$ has a lower bound, thus ensuring the stability of the theory. Typically, but not necessarily, it is a polynomial on $\varphi(\vec{n})$, of even degree

strictly larger than 2, in which the largest power has a strictly positive coefficient. Note that $\vartheta[\varphi(\vec{n})]$ does not need to have a definite parity as a function of $\varphi(\vec{n})$. The lattice squared mass parameter α is a dimensionless real parameter. The operator Δ_μ represents the finite difference of the fields across the lattice link starting at the site \vec{n} in the positive direction μ . Note that α can be negative so long as the potential $\vartheta[\varphi(\vec{n})]$ ensures the energetic stability of the theory or, in quantum terminology, the existence of its ground state. If the potential $\vartheta[\varphi(\vec{n})]$ is zero then α has to be positive, and in this case our theory reduces to the free quantum field theory of the single real scalar field $\varphi(\vec{n})$, which is exactly solvable on finite lattices, by analytic means.

If we introduce a lattice spacing a with physical dimensions of length, define the dimensionfull field $\phi(\vec{x}) = \varphi(\vec{n})/a^{(d-2)/2}$, where $\vec{x} = a\vec{n}$ are now dimensionfull real coordinates on the lattice, and observe that the lattice length is given by $L = Na$ and that the lattice volume is given by $V_L = L^d$, then we have for the action in terms of $\phi(\vec{x})$

$$S_N[\phi] = \sum_{\vec{n}} a^d \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mu=1}^d \left[\frac{\Delta_\mu \phi(\vec{x})}{a} \right]^2 + \frac{\alpha}{2a^2} \phi^2(\vec{x}) + \frac{\vartheta[\phi(\vec{x})]}{a^d} \right\}, \quad (11)$$

still on finite lattices, so that the minimum possible variation of a coordinate is $dx^\mu = a$ and the d -dimensional volumetric integration element is $d^d x = a^d$.

After that we may take the continuum limit, in which $N \rightarrow \infty$ and $a \rightarrow 0$, in such a way that the lattice length $L = Na$ remains constant, under some auxiliary conditions involving the dimensionless parameters of the model, meant at keeping the renormalized mass m_R finite in the limit. There is no need to specify these conditions in detail, because the triviality argument to be given here does not depend on these details. It is not difficult to show that, taking the continuum limit in the case $\alpha \geq 0$, the expression shown in Equation (11) tends to the usual classical expression for the action of this theory in the continuum limit, written in terms of $\phi(\vec{x})$, within a finite cubic box in d dimensions, of volume $V_L = L^d$, and using the dimensionfull potential given by $V[\phi(\vec{x})] = \vartheta[\phi(\vec{x})]/a^d$,

$$S[\phi] = \int_{V_L} d^d x \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mu=1}^d [\partial_\mu \phi(\vec{x})]^2 + \frac{m^2}{2} \phi^2(\vec{x}) + V[\phi(\vec{x})] \right\}, \quad (12)$$

where we used the relation $\alpha = m^2 a^2$. Here we see that the scaling relations between the dimensionless and dimensionfull variables, in the form used here, are required in order for the classical action, of the non-quantized theory, to assume its correct form in the continuum limit.

Since our ultimate aim is to take the continuum limit, from this point onward we will use only the real coordinates \vec{x} of the sites, both on finite lattices and in the continuum limit, except in circumstances in which the integer nature of the coordinates \vec{n} has a role to play. The observable quantities of the quantum field theory are the average values of functionals of the field $\varphi(\vec{x})$ on the statistical distribution of field configurations, also known as an ensemble, which is defined by the exponential of minus the action. These are called expectation values, and given an arbitrary observable $\mathcal{O}[\varphi]$, its expectation value is defined as the ratio of multiple integrals

$$\langle \mathcal{O} \rangle_N = \frac{\int [d\varphi]_N e^{-S_N[\varphi]} \mathcal{O}[\varphi]}{\int [d\varphi]_N e^{-S_N[\varphi]}}, \quad (13)$$

where the integrals indicated are functional integrals, that is, sums over the set of all possible field configurations $\varphi(\vec{x})$ on the lattice. On a finite N -lattice in d dimensions they can be written as multiple integrals in a real space of dimension N^d , with the measure

$$[d\varphi]_N = \prod_{\vec{n}}^{N^d} d\varphi(\vec{x}), \quad (14)$$

where the product over \vec{n} runs over all N^d lattice sites, so that it can be expressed as a d -dimensional multiple product,

$$\prod_{\vec{n}}^{N^d} \equiv \prod_{n_1=1}^N \dots \prod_{n_d=1}^N. \quad (15)$$

The integrals over $\varphi(\vec{x})$ at each site \vec{x} , shown in Equation (13), are taken from $\varphi(\vec{x}) \rightarrow -\infty$ to $\varphi(\vec{x}) \rightarrow \infty$. In the $N \rightarrow \infty$ continuum limit the integrals in Equation (13) become infinite-dimensional integrals, also known as functional integrals in the continuum, and in the limit the lattice expectation values $\langle \mathcal{O} \rangle_N$ of the observables $\mathcal{O}[\varphi]$, now written as $\mathcal{O}[\phi]$, converge by definition to the continuum expectation values $\langle \mathcal{O} \rangle$.

3 Discussion of the Hypotheses

Having defined the theory in detail, we may now discuss in greater detail, and better describe and refine, the three physical hypotheses that were introduced in Section 1.

3.1 Hypothesis 1

The fact that $g_2(\vec{0})$ is a finite and non-zero number can be easily verified to be true for many models. If we recall that we have

$$\begin{aligned} g_2(\vec{0}) &= \left\langle \varphi^2(\vec{x}) \right\rangle - \left\langle \varphi(\vec{x}) \right\rangle^2 \\ &= \left\langle \left[\varphi(\vec{x}) - \langle \varphi(\vec{x}) \rangle \right]^2 \right\rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

we can see that the fact that it is non-zero follows from the fact that this is the average of the square of a random variable that undergoes statistical fluctuations. The fact that it is finite is obvious for many models such as the Ising models in any dimension $d \geq 3$, which are identical to the $O(1)$ non-linear sigma models in the same dimensions, and for the $SO(\mathbb{N})$ non-linear sigma models for $\mathbb{N} \geq 2$ and $d \geq 3$, since in all these models the field is a real vector with \mathbb{N} components and a fixed and thus limited absolute value, so that $g_2(\vec{0})$ is bounded from below by zero and from above by some finite and non-zero number. This also holds for the free field theories in any dimension $d \geq 3$, as one can see by just calculating $g_2(\vec{0})$ directly in this case. Some examples of such calculations can be found in [7]. In the case of the $O(1)$ and $SO(\mathbb{N})$ polynomial models, again for $\mathbb{N} \geq 2$ and $d \geq 3$, there is ample numerical evidence of this fact, although in these cases, just as in the free theories, the field itself is not bounded.

This implies that $g_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1)$ is essentially a statistical correlation function. This is so because the fact that $g_2(\vec{0})$ is a finite and non-zero number implies that this function can be normalized to become 1 at the origin, thus giving origin to a standard statistical

correlation function $f_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1)$ that has the value 1 when the two values are completely correlated, such as is always the case for the correlation of any variable with itself,

$$f(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1) = \frac{g_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1)}{g_2(\vec{0})}, \quad (17)$$

where $f(\vec{0}) = 1$. In short, this hypothesis simply states that the dimensionless version of the lattice theory is a well-behaved lattice statistical system with the usual properties, such as having a well-defined two-point correlation function and a well-defined $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit leading to critical behavior, even if in dimensions other than the usual three.

3.2 Hypothesis 2

The fact that the dimensionfull two-point function $G_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1)$ is a Green's function in the continuum limit is just the usual hypothesis that guarantees that, after transformation to Minkowski space, the resulting function represents the propagation of particles, a property due to which it is known as the propagator. The renormalized mass m_R appears explicitly in this function when it is written in momentum space, and there is propagation of particles so long as m_R is not infinite in the continuum limit. What this means is that in the continuum limit the dimensionfull version of the lattice theory, when transformed to Minkowski space, becomes a well-behaved field theory with the usual properties, such as the propagation of particles with finite masses.

The consequences of Hypothesis 1 for the behavior of the dimensionfull two-point function $G_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1)$ at the origin are immediate. Given that the scaling relation between the dimensionfull field $\phi(\vec{x})$ and the dimensionless field $\varphi(\vec{n})$, of finite N -lattices, as we saw in Section 2, is given by

$$\phi(\vec{x}) = \frac{\varphi(\vec{x})}{a^{(d-2)/2}}, \quad (18)$$

this implies that a similar scaling relation holds between the dimensionfull two-point function $G_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1)$ and the dimensionless two-point function $g_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1)$, given their definitions in Equations (1) and (3), namely that we have

$$G_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1) = \frac{g_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1)}{a^{d-2}}, \quad (19)$$

and in particular that we have at the origin

$$G_2(\vec{0}) = \frac{g_2(\vec{0})}{a^{d-2}}. \quad (20)$$

This implies that, for any spacetime dimension $d \geq 3$, and since according to Hypothesis 1 we have that $g_2(\vec{0})$ is some finite and non-zero number in the continuum limit, $G_2(\vec{0})$ diverges to infinity as an inverse power of a , in any continuum limit, in which we necessarily must have that $a \rightarrow 0$, if the lattice is to approach the continuum in any reasonable sense. This is consistent with the fact that $G_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1)$ is a Green's function, and in this way we have verified the consistency of the first two hypotheses.

3.3 Hypothesis 3

The definition of the theory on the lattice was given in Section 2, covering in particular the process of taking the continuum limit, with $N \rightarrow \infty$ and $a \rightarrow 0$. As we saw there, in order to be able to take the continuum limit unequivocally, the dimensionfull field and

the corresponding dimensionfull parameters must be introduced. However, the dynamics on the lattice are better described in terms of the dimensionless variables and parameters. Both sets of variables are useful, and in fact necessary, for a better understanding of the structure of the theory. The scaling relations between them, in the form used here, are equally required by the structure, in order for the continuum limit of either version of the theory, quantized or non-quantized, to result in the correct forms of their actions.

In order to give the physical interpretation of the theory we must introduce the concept of block variables. The central physical idea leading to the definition of these variables is that, due to the uncertainty principle, one cannot measure any quantities at single points, but instead can measure only averages over regions of finite and non-zero size. Therefore, in terms of the measurable physical quantities one must choose a finite and non-zero length scale ℓ , as a finite and non-zero fraction of the size L of the lattice, and reformulate the theory in terms of average fields over regions with size given by that length scale. These are the block-averaged field variables.

A block variable at a certain scale is defined as an average of the field $\varphi(\vec{x})$ over a proper sub-volume within the lattice, that for simplicity we imagine to be a d -dimensional cube, which we will refer to as a block. If $N_B < N$ is the number of sites along the linear size ℓ of that region of the lattice, then the ratio $N_B/N = \ell/L$, where ℓ is therefore the linear size of the block, is the ratio that defines the blocking scale, since it is the ratio of the linear size ℓ of the block by the linear size L of the whole lattice. The block variable is given by

$$\bar{\varphi}(\vec{x}_B) = \frac{1}{N_B^d} \sum_{\vec{n}}^{N_B^d} \varphi(\vec{x}), \quad (21)$$

where the sum over \vec{n} runs over a d -dimensional cube containing N_B^d sites located around the site \vec{x}_B at its center, which thus characterizes the location of the block. Note that there is no castellation of the lattice involved here, at every site \vec{x} we calculate this block variable, so that the averages at nearby sites are taken over overlapping sets of sites.

The block-transformation process works like this: the fundamental field $\varphi(\vec{x})$ has a statistical distribution given by $\exp(-S_N[\varphi])$. If we let the underlying dynamics of the fundamental field run, then this underlying dynamics implies a corresponding dynamics of the block-averaged field $\bar{\varphi}(\vec{x})$, since according to Equation (21) it is defined in terms of that fundamental field. Therefore this block-averaged field acquires a statistical distribution of its own, and this distribution can subsequently be encoded as $\exp(-S_E[\bar{\varphi}])$, where the effective action $S_E[\bar{\varphi}]$ is a functional of the block-averaged field $\bar{\varphi}(\vec{x})$.

This effective action encodes all that can be measured within the theory, at or above the blocking length scale ℓ . Due to the symmetries of both the lattice and the model, the form of this effective action can usually be guessed without too much difficulty, up to the values of a few parameters. By and large the form of $S_E[\bar{\varphi}]$ is the same as that of $S_N[\varphi]$. In terms of the dimensionless block-averaged field we have

$$S_E[\bar{\varphi}] = \sum_{\vec{n}}^{N^d} \frac{1}{Z} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mu=1}^d [\Delta_{\mu} \bar{\varphi}(\vec{x})]^2 + \frac{\alpha_R}{2} \bar{\varphi}^2(\vec{x}) + \vartheta[\bar{\varphi}(\vec{x})] \right\}, \quad (22)$$

where α_R is the renormalized version of the parameter α , Z is a possible field renormalization factor, usually a number of the order of 1, and the potential $\vartheta[\bar{\varphi}(\vec{x})]$ contains the renormalized interaction parameters such as λ_R . We say that the effective action contains the renormalized versions of the bare parameters of the underlying fundamental theory.

The physical character of the model is defined by the set of all possible effective actions, at all finite and non-zero length scales $\ell < L$ within the lattice. In this way, we see that the underlying fundamental structure represents the physics of the model at all possible length scales, but that it involves quantities which cannot be directly measured, while the block-averaged structure represents all that can be measured at or above a certain length scale. Therefore, if we demonstrate some property that is valid for the effective actions at all length scales, then we are in fact showing a property of the underlying fundamental structure.

4 Proof of Gaussian Triviality

Let us take as our set of random variables the values of the dimensionless lattice field $\varphi(\vec{x})$ at all the N^d sites \vec{x} . In the continuum limit we have that $N \rightarrow \infty$, so that this becomes an infinite set of random variables. Given the translation symmetries of the model on the lattice, it is immediately apparent that these random variables are all identically distributed, by construction. As we already discussed in Section 1, our Hypothesis 1 implies that this distribution has a finite width. This establishes two of the basic hypotheses of the CLT. Let us continue our argument by showing that in the continuum limit these random variables all become independent from each other.

We do this by showing that all the random variables $\varphi(\vec{x})$ become completely uncorrelated from one another in the continuum limit. In order to do this, consider the dimensionfull two-point function $G_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1)$ and the dimensionless two-point function $g_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1)$. We have shown that these two functions are related as shown in Equation (19). Using now our Hypothesis 2, since $G_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1)$ is a Green's function, it is a regular function away from the origin, that is, for $\vec{x}_2 \neq \vec{x}_1$. Therefore we have for the corresponding dimensionless two-point function

$$g_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1) = a^{d-2}G_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1), \quad (23)$$

for all $\vec{x}_2 \neq \vec{x}_1$. Since in any continuum limit we must have $a \rightarrow 0$, and since according to our Hypothesis 2 in that limit $G_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1)$ is a finite number for $\vec{x}_2 \neq \vec{x}_1$, it follows that for $d \geq 3$, in any continuum limit, we have that

$$g_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1) \rightarrow 0, \quad (24)$$

for all $\vec{x}_2 \neq \vec{x}_1$. Since $g_2(\vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1)$ is essentially a correlation function between the two values of the field $\varphi(\vec{x}_2)$ and $\varphi(\vec{x}_1)$, we must conclude that in the continuum limit the fields $\varphi(\vec{x})$ at any two different positions becomes completely uncorrelated from one another. Therefore in the continuum limit the dimensionless fields $\varphi(\vec{x})$ at different positions become an infinite set of **iid** random variables with a distribution that has a finite width, as implied by Hypothesis 1.

Let us now consider the dimensionless and dimensionfull block-averaged variables $\bar{\varphi}(\vec{x})$ and $\bar{\phi}(\vec{x})$, which are related to each other in the same way that $\varphi(\vec{x})$ and $\phi(\vec{x})$ are, as shown in Equation (18), so that we have

$$\bar{\phi}(\vec{x}) = \frac{\bar{\varphi}(\vec{x})}{a^{(d-2)/2}}. \quad (25)$$

The block averages are calculated within groups of N_B^d sites, with a constant ratio N_B/N . Therefore, in the continuum limit, in which we have that $N \rightarrow \infty$, we must also have

$N_B \rightarrow \infty$, so that as the continuum limit is taken the block averages are taken over progressively larger sets of random variables, in numbers that increase without bound.

This puts us within the realm of validity of the CLT, and therefore we conclude that in the continuum limit the block-averaged fields $\bar{\varphi}(\vec{x}_B) = \bar{\varphi}_B$ and $\bar{\phi}(\vec{x}_B) = \bar{\phi}_B$, for any block \vec{x}_B , both have purely Gaussian distributions, with different average values, and with widths that go to zero at different rates, but both tending very fast to Gaussian distribution as the continuum limit is taken. According to the CLT, in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ continuum limit the shifted and rescaled random variable \bar{Y}_B for a block, given by

$$\bar{Y}_B = N_B^{d/2} (\bar{\varphi}_B - \langle \varphi \rangle), \quad (26)$$

has a statistical distribution of values that approaches a Gaussian distribution of average value zero and a squared width given by $\sigma^2 = g_2(\vec{0})$. Writing this same expression in terms of the dimensionfull blocked field $\bar{\phi}_B$ we have

$$\bar{Y}_B = N_B \ell^{d/2-1} (\bar{\phi}_B - \langle \phi \rangle). \quad (27)$$

Note that in this case the rescaling factor involving N_B is independent of the spacetime dimension d . This shows us how we must rescale the random variables $\bar{\phi}_B$ in order to get in the continuum limit a normal distribution with a finite and non-zero width. The consequences of the CLT, when applied to Equations (26) and (27), then imply that the effective actions $S_E[\bar{\varphi}]$ and $S_E[\bar{\phi}]$ must be purely quadratic in the continuum limit, so that all the existing coupling constants must be zero. The most general form of the action $S_E[\bar{\varphi}]$ is therefore that of a full quadratic form on the dimensionless block-averaged fields $\bar{\varphi}(\vec{x})$ which, omitting field-independent terms, is given by

$$S_E[\bar{\varphi}] = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{\vec{n}} \frac{1}{Z} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mu=1}^d [\Delta_\mu \bar{\varphi}(\vec{x})]^2 + \frac{\alpha_R}{2} \bar{\varphi}^2(\vec{x}) - \alpha_R \bar{v}_R \bar{\varphi}(\vec{x}) \right\}, \quad (28)$$

where α_R is the renormalized square mass parameter and \bar{v}_R is the expectation value of the block-averaged field $\bar{\varphi}(\vec{x})$. In terms of the dimensionfull block-averaged fields $\bar{\phi}(\vec{x})$ we must also have a purely quadratic action, given by

$$S_E[\bar{\phi}] = \oint_{V_L} d^d x \frac{1}{Z} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mu=1}^d [\partial_\mu \bar{\phi}(\vec{x})]^2 + \frac{m_R^2}{2} \bar{\phi}^2(\vec{x}) - m_R^2 \bar{V}_R \bar{\phi}(\vec{x}) \right\}, \quad (29)$$

where we used the relation $\alpha_R = m_R^2 a^2$, m_R is the renormalized mass and \bar{V}_R is the expectation value of the block-averaged field $\bar{\phi}(\vec{x})$. This holds true for every block-average length scale ℓ . Once again we see here that the scaling relations between the dimensionless and dimensionfull variables, in the form used here, are required by the structure of the theory, this time in order for the classical action that represents the classical limit of the quantized theory to assume its correct form in the continuum limit. Note that the constant Z does not disturb the quadratic character of either one of these actions. If one wishes to, one can eliminate it using a simple finite rescaling of the fields by $1/\sqrt{Z}$.

In conclusion, in the continuum limit the model contains only two physically relevant parameters, a possibly non-zero vacuum expectation value \bar{V}_R of the field and the mass m_R of the particles. In other words, the model is trivial, in the sense that all its expectation values can be obtained from a related Gaussian model, regardless of the form of the potential appearing in the fundamental action. In order to actually do this, we can just restart the definition of the quantum theory, using the exact Gaussian form of $S_E[\bar{\varphi}]$ as the new fundamental action, with the parameter α_R playing the role of the parameter α .

4.1 Decoupling the Two Limits

When going through the argument at it was presented above, one could be forgiven for having some doubts about the validity of the application of the CLT. This is so because in this argument we take the $N \rightarrow \infty$ continuum limit in such a way that two independent things happen at the same time during this limit. First, the correlations between fields $\varphi(\vec{x})$ at different sites go to zero as a power of a , and second the number N_B^d of random variables within a block goes to infinity, and therefore so goes the number of random variables that we are averaging over. Let us name the first limit, which takes us to the state of statistical independence of the random variables, as the continuum limit, and the second limit, which takes us to a situation in which we are taking averages over infinite sets of random variables, as the CLT limit.

One could argue that the CLT is valid only if the random variables being averaged over are already completely independent by the time we add them up. Since in the way of taking the limit described above the random variables are becoming independent, but are not yet completely independent during the limit, one might be led to think that this simultaneous combination of the two limits makes it less clear that the theorem is applicable. However, it is very simple to circumvent this apparent difficulty by simply decoupling the two limits.

In order to do this we first take the continuum limit, so that the random variables within a block become truly independent from one another. If we consider the situation within any one block, by the end of this first limit we have within that block an infinite number of truly independent variables $\varphi(\vec{x})$, with a statistical distribution having a finite and non-zero width $\sigma^2 = g_2(\vec{0})$. We may now start taking progressively larger finite numbers N_S of random variables within that block, and averaging them, so as to obtain partial averages over the block located at \vec{x}_B ,

$$\bar{\varphi}(\vec{x}_B) = \frac{1}{N_S} \sum_{\vec{n}}^{N_S} \varphi(\vec{x}). \quad (30)$$

Since the random variables being averaged over are now truly independent, we may now take the CLT limit, in which $N_S \rightarrow \infty$, use the theorem and thus conclude that the block random variables $\bar{\varphi}(\vec{x})$, when dully shifted and rescaled, all have one and the same Gaussian distribution, with average $\langle \varphi \rangle$ and squared width σ^2 .

Note that, since the final situation regarding the nature of the random variables within a block, as well as the final situation regarding their distribution, is the same in either way in which we may take the limits, it seems that there is nothing actually wrong in taking the limit as implied by our first argument above.

5 Proof of Interaction Triviality

In order to discuss how the property of triviality in the sense proven in Section 4 relates to the non-existence of inter-particle interactions, let us examine a particular class of models, in which the potential is given by a simple even power of the field. Consider the case of the so-called φ^{2p} models in $d \geq 3$ dimensions, with the integer powers given by the integer $p \geq 2$. The action of this model is given in terms of the dimensionless field by

$$S_N[\varphi] = \sum_{\vec{n}}^{N^d} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mu=1}^d [\Delta_\mu \varphi(\vec{x})]^2 + \frac{\alpha}{2} \varphi^2(\vec{x}) + \frac{\lambda}{2p} \varphi^{2p}(\vec{x}) \right\}, \quad (31)$$

where λ is a strictly positive real number. The same action written in terms of the dimensionfull field, still on finite lattices, is given by

$$S_N[\phi] = \sum_{\vec{n}} a^d \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mu=1}^d \left[\frac{\Delta_\mu \phi(\vec{x})}{a} \right]^2 + \frac{\alpha}{2a^2} \phi^2(\vec{x}) + \frac{\Lambda}{2p} \phi^{2p}(\vec{x}) \right\}. \quad (32)$$

The relation between the dimensionless coupling parameter λ and the corresponding dimensionfull coupling parameter Λ is easily determined to be $\Lambda = \lambda a^{pd-2p-d}$, and therefore there is a similar relation for the corresponding renormalized quantities that appear in the two forms of the corresponding effective action,

$$\Lambda_R = \lambda_R a^{pd-2p-d}. \quad (33)$$

The quantity Λ_R is the parameter that describes the inter-particle interactions within the model. If it is zero in the continuum limit, then there are no such inter-particle interactions, and the model reduces to a free field theory in that continuum limit. Our first task here is to show that in almost all cases the fact that $\lambda_R \rightarrow 0$ in the limit already implies that $\Lambda_R \rightarrow 0$ as well. Since we have that in the continuum limit $\lambda_R \rightarrow 0$ for all $d \geq 3$ and all $p \geq 2$, as was shown in Section 4, it follows from Equation (33) that if $pd - 2p - d \geq 0$ then we have that $\Lambda_R \rightarrow 0$ in the limit. Let us examine this issue in a case-by-case basis, for each relevant value of the spacetime dimension d .

In the case $d = 4$ this condition reduces to $p \geq 2$, so that in four dimensions all these models are trivial in the sense that there are no inter-particle interactions. In the case $d = 5$ the condition reduces to $p \geq 5/3$, and since we already have the limitation that $p \geq 2$, in all these models there are no inter-particle interactions as well. The same happens for all higher spacetime dimensions $d \geq 6$, for all $p \geq 2$. The one case that must be examined with particular care here is the case $d = 3$, in which the condition reduces to $p \geq 3$. So we see that in this case there is a single possible exception, for the case $p = 2$. For all higher powers $2p$ we still get a trivial model with no inter-particle interactions in $d = 3$. In this single exceptional case, for $d = 3$ and $p = 2$, we have

$$\Lambda_R = \frac{\lambda_R}{a}. \quad (34)$$

Since we have that both $\lambda_R \rightarrow 0$ and $a \rightarrow 0$ in the continuum limit, it is in principle possible that in this single case there can be a finite and non-zero value for Λ_R in the limit. The question of whether or not this is possible hinges on the possibility of adjusting the bare parameters α and λ as N increases, in order to make $\lambda_R \rightarrow 0$ exactly as a . Note that α and λ are subject to another constraint, since the point (α, λ) must approach the critical curve in the parameter plane of the model as $N \rightarrow \infty$, if the renormalized mass m_R is to be kept finite. Therefore we see that the answer to this question is far from simple, since it is not obvious that such a limit can be arranged.

However, we can refer back to the CLT, applied directly to the dimensionfull variables, and in particular to its consequence expressed in Equation (29), in order to conclude that also in this case the theory cannot contain inter-particle interactions. This is so because, if one could take this limit so that Λ_R resulted non-null, then there would have to be a quartic term in Equation (29), which is ruled out by the CLT. We may therefore conclude that there is no way to chose the behavior of the bare parameters α and λ so that the continuum limit of Equation (34) results non-null. Or, in other words, in every continuum limit of this particular theory we must have that $\lambda_R \rightarrow 0$ faster than a .

6 Conclusions and Outlook

We have shown that a very large class of models of scalar fields are trivial in the sense that in the continuum limit they are equivalent to corresponding Gaussian models, and also that in all cases they contain no inter-particle interactions. The proof presented used directly the definition of the models on the lattice, and there was no intermediate transformation into some other representation. It should be noted that this is the way in which essentially all the numerical simulations that probe the question of triviality are constructed. The proof implies, in particular, that all the $\lambda\varphi^{2p}$ models for $p \geq 2$ in all spacetime dimensions $d \geq 3$ are trivial in the sense of being equivalent to corresponding purely Gaussian models, and that all of those are also trivial in the sense that they contain no inter-particle interactions.

This proof originated from the construction of a clear understanding of the structure of the definition of quantum field theories on the lattice, involving in particular the study of the behavior of the dimensionless versus the dimensionfull variables and parameters, and of the scaling relations between the two sets. These two sets of variables are both needed for the various aspects of the description of the models, and the set of fixed relations between them can be used to determine the behavior of the models in the continuum limit. That structure involves four versions of the field, the dimensionless fundamental field $\varphi(\vec{x})$, the dimensionfull fundamental field $\phi(\vec{x})$, the dimensionless blocked field $\bar{\varphi}(\vec{x})$ and the dimensionfull blocked field $\bar{\phi}(\vec{x})$, each one of them with particular properties and particular uses.

For example, the conclusion about the two-point function of $\varphi(\vec{x})$, expressed in Equation (24), leading to the fact that these variables are completely uncorrelated in the continuum limit, might seem troubling at first sight. But it is not really a problem, because the field $\varphi(\vec{x})$ has no dynamic role in the limit. In fact, if one considers the definition of the block-averaged variables $\bar{\varphi}(\vec{x})$ given in Equation (21), with their averages over overlapping sets of sites, which means that there are clear correlations between fields $\bar{\varphi}(\vec{x})$ at nearby sites, one can see that the relevant physical correlations are being re-encoded into these blocked variables. This eventually leads to the fact that the two-point function of the dimensionfull block-averaged field $\bar{\phi}(\vec{x})$ is a completely well-behaved function in the continuum limit, being finite and non-zero everywhere. In this way the variables $\bar{\phi}(\vec{x})$ have the role of taking the relevant physical correlations to the very end of the definition process.

In addition to this, if one looks at Equations (26) and (27), one can see that the width of the distributions of both $\bar{\varphi}(\vec{x})$ and $\bar{\phi}(\vec{x})$ go to zero in the continuum limit, and that in the case of $\bar{\phi}(\vec{x})$ the way in which this happens is independent of the spacetime dimension d . Since this means that the variable $\bar{\phi}(\vec{x})$ ceases to undergo quantum fluctuations in the limit, the corresponding effective action shown in Equation (29) becomes a classical action in the limit. In fact, it is the action that describes the classical limit of the quantum theory. Once the structure is well understood, the actual proof of the theorem becomes in fact very simple. Extensive numerical work had an essential role in helping to establish this clear understanding of the structure, as had many detailed analytical lattice calculations in the case of the free theory, the single case in which we have complete analytical control over the theory, and are able to calculate anything that is required.

It should be pointed out that the scaling relations between the two versions of the variables, dimensionless and dimensionfull, that play such a crucial role in the arguments presented, are implied by the very definition of the theory, and are required so that the actions in the continuum limit assume their recognizable forms. In the case of the fundamental action, they are required so that the action in the continuum limit converges to the known classical action of the non-quantized theory. Similarly, in the case of the effective

actions they are required so that the effective action in the continuum limit converges to the classical action which represents the classical limit of the quantized theory.

The proof presented in this paper is very general, and not particularly dependent on the fact that the fields are spacetime scalars. It could apply just as well to other types of fields, or rather to individual components of such fields. The content of the proof can be interpreted as the fact that terms in the Lagrangian density that contain three or more powers of one and the same field function do not survive the quantization process. The resulting effective actions will always turn out to be at most quadratic on every field component involved, eventually leading to the absence of this type of inter-particle interaction. For illustration, as one example of a notoriously non-linear field theory involving vector fields, let us take the non-Abelian gauge theories. For simplicity, we will use here their open versions, written on the tangent spaces at the identity elements of the gauge groups. The field tensor $F_{\mu\nu}^a$ in such theories can be written in terms of the vector potential A_μ^a as

$$F_{\mu\nu}^a = \partial_\mu A_\nu^a - \partial_\nu A_\mu^a + g f_{bc}^a A_\mu^b A_\nu^c, \quad (35)$$

where the parameter g is the gauge coupling constant and f_{bc}^a are the structure constants of the Lie algebra of the gauge group. This is an expression which is clearly non-linear on A_μ^a . In a $SU(N)$ theory each vector field A_μ^a not only has d spacetime vector components indexed by μ , but a number of $SU(N)$ components indexed by a . The Lagrangian density for the vector field is given by

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{4} \delta_{ab} F_{\mu\nu}^a F^{b\mu\nu}, \quad (36)$$

which may give the impression that it contains components of the vector field with up to the fourth power. However, this is a false impression, because the structure constants f_{bc}^a of the Lie algebra that appear in Equation (35) are antisymmetric in the two lower indices, so that the components of the structure constants are zero in the case $b = c$. This prevents the square of any single vector field component to appear in Equation (35), and therefore these components can appear in the Lagrangian density shown in Equation (36) at most with the power two. Therefore, all physically meaningful interaction terms seem to be necessarily multi-linear, possibly including quadratic factors as well, thus involving several different field components, rather than being simply non-linear on a single field component.

It is noteworthy that the fact that the structure constants are antisymmetric in the two lower indices is crucially important to guarantee that the field tensor $F_{\mu\nu}^a$ is antisymmetric in the spacetime indices, as it should be. Because the structure constants are antisymmetric in the two lower indices we can write the field tensor as

$$F_{\mu\nu}^a = \partial_\mu A_\nu^a - \partial_\nu A_\mu^a + \frac{1}{2} g f_{bc}^a \left(A_\mu^b A_\nu^c - A_\nu^b A_\mu^c \right), \quad (37)$$

thus showing explicitly that it is antisymmetric in the pair of spacetime indices (μ, ν) . In any case, this discussion shows that the non-Abelian gauge theories are immune from the consequences of the type of proof presented here. So is quantum electrodynamics. One might even think that this fact could be used to select these theories among other alternative theories, instead of the usual perturbative renormalizability criterion.

While the proof presented here cannot be considered as a rigorous mathematical proof from first principles, since it depends on some physically motivated hypotheses, it does expose clearly the underlying structure involved in the definition of the quantum field theories on the lattice, that results in the proof presented. We should point out that the construction of a rigorous ab-initio mathematical proof was not the aim of this paper. The aim was

to expose as clearly as possible the underlying structure and propose a new, different way of looking at the problem. The completion of this proof as a rigorous mathematical proof could possibly be accomplished by the proof of the first two hypotheses, based on some appropriate mathematical hypotheses about the structure of any particular model that one may want to explore.

The author is aware of the fact that the results presented here may be in conflict with some results obtained by other means, in particular those obtained using the representation of lattice quantum field theories by ensembles of random walks. It is possible that the cause of this is the fact that random walks in the continuum limit are, by their very definition, continuous paths. They are typically non-differentiable, but continuous nonetheless. On the other hand, it has been shown decades ago that in lattice quantum field theory the fields are discontinuous at all points and in all Cartesian directions, in the continuum limit from the lattice [8,9]. The proof of this fact is based on the fact that the expectation value of the squared finite difference of the dimensionless field across any given link,

$$\left\langle [\Delta_\mu \varphi(\vec{x})]^2 \right\rangle, \quad (38)$$

where there is no sum over μ , does not go to zero in the continuum limit, at any lattice position and in any lattice direction. Since the same expectation value, if calculated only over an ensemble of continuous configurations, is clearly zero in the continuum limit, it follows that, in the ensemble of configurations obtained in the continuum limit from the structure on the lattice, the set of all continuous field configurations is a zero-measure subset of the set of all possible configurations. Hence, it is not surprising that there may be cases in which the conclusions from these two approaches may fail to match each other.

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